

Graphical Abstract

Analysis of Colchicine-induced Effects on Hepatoma and Hepatocyte Cells by Atomic Force Microscopy

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Abstract

Biomechanical properties of cells are altered by many diseases. Cancer cell metastasis is related to the properties such as the cell stiffness that influences cell proliferation, differentiation and migration. In this paper, we used an atomic force microscope to analyze the colchicine-induced effects on the mechanical properties of hepatocyte (HL-7702 cells) and hepatoma cells (SMCC-7721 cells) in culture at the nanoscale. The cells were exposed to a solution with a normal dose of colchicine for two, four and six hours. Surface topographic images showed that colchicine decreased the stability of the cytoskeleton. After the same six-hour treatment in a solution with a normal dose of colchicine, the biomechanical properties of HL-7702 cells were almost unchanged. However, the stiffness and the adhesion force of the SMCC-7721 cells were clearly increased (more than twofold of the normal values), especially after four hours. The deformability of SMCC-7721 cancer cells was significantly decreased within the six-hour treatment in the solution with a normal dose of colchicine. Analysis of the biomechanical properties of post-treatment hepatoma cells provided a complementary explanation for the mechanism of action of colchicine on cells at the nanoscale. This method is expected to allow the monitoring of potential metastatic cancer cell changes, thus preventing the emergence and the transmission of disease, and improving the diagnosis of cancer.

Keywords: Atomic force microscope, hepatocyte (HL-7702), hepatoma cell (SMCC-7721), colchicine, biomechanical properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that cancer mortality should continue to rise within the next 15 years, reaching about 11.4 million deaths worldwide by 2030^{1, 2}. The primary reasons for the high mortality of cancer are the invasion and the metastasis of tumor cells to other parts of the body^{3, 4}. Therefore, understanding the mechanisms of cancer cell migration and motility, and attempting to restrain them during carcinogenesis have been the focuses of recent research^{5, 6}. Many researchers have reported that cancer cell metastasis is influenced by cell deformability, which is related to stiffness⁷⁻¹². Therefore, biomechanical properties of cells are used to study cancer cell metastasis because stiffness influences cell proliferation, differentiation, and migration. In this regard, analysis of the mechanical properties of cells plays a major role in the detection of biological deformability and other characteristics¹³.

Many techniques have been developed to measure the biomechanical properties of cells for different applications, e.g. atomic force microscopy (AFM)^{6, 7, 12, 14-16}, magnetic twisting cytometry^{9, 17}, micropipette aspiration¹⁸ and optical tweezers¹⁹. Compared with the other methods,

AFM has the advantages of ultra-high resolution, high reliability and multi-dimensional information detection²⁰⁻²², which are the characteristics essential for the study of cell elasticity and deformability. Using AFM, Li et al.²³ and Nikkhah et al.²⁴ showed that nonmalignant breast epithelial cells exhibited a significant higher Young's modulus than their malignant counterparts. Park et al.²⁵ showed that normal BALB 3T3 fibroblasts were significantly less deformable than SV-T2 fibroblasts tested using AFM. Liu et al.²⁶ measured the biomechanical properties of living SMCC-7721 cells before and after a treatment with fullereneol solution. They found that stiffness was decreased after the treatment. Francius et al.²⁷ observed that a mutant of the bacteria *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* was twice as stiff as its wild type. Vesenka et al.²⁸ found that the deformation of tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) resulted in a Young's modulus of about 1 MPa, while TMV was irreversibly damaged above 40 MPa. Cross et al.^{6, 7} reported that healthy cells were 30% stiffer than metastatic cancer cells. These findings regarding different cancers suggest that the analysis of the biomechanical properties of cancer cells by AFM could become a tool for cancer diagnoses^{14, 23, 29}.

The main target of anticancer drugs is the cytoskeleton³⁰⁻³². The different structures of the cytoskeleton are reflected in their different biomechanical properties, which play a significant role in cell division, cell transport, chromosome segregation, and gene expression. As an

alkaloid agent, colchicine is a common drug that has been used for the prevention and the treatment of gout for more than a century^{33, 34}. Recently, some researchers discovered that colchicine, as a natural product, had an anticancer effect able to hinder the polymerization of microtubules and block the cell cycle procession^{35, 36}. Microtubules are major components of the cytoskeleton. Kuo et al.³⁷ found that colchicine was associated with a reduced risk of incident cancer in male patients with gout. Bhattacharya et al.³⁸ reported that colchicine could induce senescence and autophagy in lung cancer (A549) cells.

The biological method is more frequently used to study the anticancer action of colchicine. However, the method cannot explain the mechanism of colchicine action on the surface of cancer cells. So far, no studies have reported the biomechanical analysis of colchicine-induced effects on hepatocyte (HL-7702) cells³⁹ and hepatoma (SMCC-7721) cells⁴⁰ at the nanoscale. Therefore, in this work, we mainly focused on the stiffness and stickiness properties of hepatocytes and hepatoma cells before and after the treatment with colchicine solutions for two, four and six hours, using AFM. Changes in the biomechanical properties of a single cell were observed and measured at the nanoscale. Results regarding the cell surface profile and its biomechanical properties exhibited the mechanical changes in the cytoskeleton, cell deformability and cytoadherence. This method is expected to provide a potential complementary diagnosis and a

treatment aid for cancer.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Cell Lines and Cell Culture

Human hepatic (HL-7702) cells and human hepatocellular carcinoma (SMCC-7721) cells were procured from the cell bank at the Chinese Academy of Sciences.

HL-7702 and SMCC-7721 cells were cultured in the 1640 culture solution supplemented with 10% of fetal bovine serum (FBS). In the experiment, cells were plated on glass coverslips (18 mm; square) at a density of 1.0×10^5 cells/mL (1 mL per coverslip) in a 38-mm plastic Petri culture dishes. Then cells were incubated at 37°C in a humidified incubator with 5% of CO₂ for 24 hours.

2.2 Colchicine Solution

In this work, the colchicine drug was provided by Xishuangbanna Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd, China (No. H53021369). The equivalent of a colchicine dose of 0.5 mg per pill was used in this study. One pill was dissolved in 1 mL of deionized water. According to the blood proportion of one person (7%-8%)⁴¹, the solution was filtered and diluted 50 times with deionized water. In the experiment, a 2-mL culture solution and the

20- μ L colchicine solution were added to each culture dish. The concentration of 0.1 μ g/mL colchicine solution complied with the usual prescribed dose.

2.3 Indentation System

The NanoWizard[®] 3 NanoOptics BioScience AFM System (JPK Instruments AG, Berlin, Germany) was used as an imaging and indentation system to obtain the images and detect the biomechanical properties of HL-7702 and SMCC-7721 cells in culture (for a schematic diagram of the AFM, see Fig. 1(a)). The diagram of the indentation process is shown in Fig. 1(b). This process consisted of two main parts: loading (Fig. 1(c)) and unloading (Fig. 1(d)).

In this work, we used a square pyramidal tip. During the loading stage, the sensed reaction force remains below the noise level which means that the long-range force between the cytomembrane and the tip of the indenter has a smaller gradient than the cantilever spring constant^{42, 43}. On the other hand, the tip-cell surface adhesive force was characterized by a short-range force that remained negligible until the AFM tip was in the intimate contact with the cell during the loading stage. According to Hertz's theory⁴⁴, for the elastic indentation with a spherical or conical indenter, F is equal to^{26, 43, 45}

$$F = F_e = \frac{E}{1 - \nu^2} \frac{\tan \alpha}{\sqrt{2}} h^2 \quad (1)$$

where F is the sum of the elastic force and the adhesive force of the sample; F_e is the elastic force of an ideal regular square pyramidal AFM tip; E is the Young's modulus; α is the half-cone-angle of a pyramid tip; ν is the Poisson's ratio of the sample, and h is the indenting depth. Before unloading begins, the intimate contact evokes a short-range adhesion force and forms adhesive bonds (the ligand-receptor binding affinity) and thus the adhesive force is characterized by the pull-force (illustrated by a negative force in Fig. 1(d)) needed to break the binder during the tip retraction. During the unloading process, F_a plays a leading role and is related to the tip-cell surface contact area A_c , and the adhesion energy W_a . The tip-surface adhesive force can be expressed as⁴³

$$F_a = -\frac{dW_a}{dh} = -\frac{\tan\alpha}{\cos\alpha \cdot \pi^2} 32\gamma h' \quad (2)$$

where γ is the work of adhesive force at the contact interface, and h' is the maximized elevation of cells (Fig. 1(d)).

3. RESULTS

The cells were plated on glass coverslips in culture dishes for 24 hours. Then, a phosphate buffered saline (PBS) was used to wash and remove unadhered and dead cells. In the experiments, the topographies and mechanical properties of HL-7702 and SMCC-7721 cells were

acquired by the quantitative imaging (QI) function of the AFM. The measurements were made by a non-conductive silicon nitride cantilever with a spring constant of 0.06 N/m, and the radius of the square pyramidal probe tip was 20 nm (DNP, Bruker). The calibrated value of the spring constant of the probe was 0.062 N/m. The setpoint value of 2.545 nN was used in the experiments. Ten cells were selected for measurement among HL-7702 and SMCC-7721 cells, and each of the ten points of the cells was measured three times.

3.1 Topographies

The topography of one HL-7702 control cell is shown in Fig. 2(a). The cell was treated with the colchicine solution for two hours (Fig. 2 (b)), four hours (Fig. 2 (c)) and six hours (Fig. 2 (d)). The average roughness value was 1.644 μm for the control cell, 1.613 μm for the cell treated for two hours, 1.579 μm for the cell treated for four hours and 1.388 μm for the cell treated for six hours. A significant reduction in the cytoskeleton sharpness was observed after the treatment. The topography of a liver cancer SMCC-7721 cell is shown in Fig. 2(e). The topographies of the cells after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two hours, four hours and six hours are shown in Figs. 2(f)-(h). The average roughness value was 1.513 μm for the control cell, 1.466 μm for the cell treated for two hours, 1.664 μm for the cell treated for four hours and 2.037 μm for

the cell treated for six hours. The cell nucleus became clearer after the treatment and the cytoskeletal structure was clearly changed. The results indicated that the colchicine solution altered the skeleton structures of HL-7702 and SMCC-7721 cells at the nanoscale.

Fig. 2(i) shows the average height distributions of the HL-7702 and SMCC-7721 cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours. The average height of the HL-7702 control cell was $5.75 \pm 1.85 \mu\text{m}$. The average heights of the HL-7702 cells after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours were $6.22 \pm 0.92 \mu\text{m}$, $6.34 \pm 1.56 \mu\text{m}$ and $5.87 \pm 0.85 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The average heights of the SMCC-7721 cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours were $5.22 \pm 0.89 \mu\text{m}$, $5.87 \pm 0.82 \mu\text{m}$, $6.41 \pm 0.86 \mu\text{m}$ and $7.38 \pm 0.66 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The average height of HL-7702 cells remained unchanged while the average height of SMCC-7721 cells was obviously increased after six hours of treatment.

3.2 Biomechanical Properties

Force-indentation curves in the loading stage for the control cells and the treatment cells for two, four and six hours are shown in Fig. 3. The curves of the HL-7702 cells appear more concentrated than the curves of the SMCC-7721 cells. The slope changes of the curves at the contact

critical point between the tip and the HL-7702 cell were not noticeable, as shown in Fig. 3(a). The slopes of the curves at the contact critical point for SMCC-7721 cells were increased with the increase of treatment time, as shown in Fig. 3(b).

For the HL-7702 cells, the average elasticity modulus was slightly decreased after six hours of treatment compared with the elastic modulus of the control cells, as shown in Fig. 4(c). The average elasticity moduli of the HL-7702 cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours were 360.01 ± 61.26 Pa, 318.89 ± 57.35 Pa, 322.89 ± 59.97 Pa and 249.29 ± 26.24 Pa, respectively. The distribution of the elastic moduli indicated that no significant change occurred, as shown in Fig. 4(a). Fig. 4(b) shows the statistical distribution of the elastic moduli for the SMCC-7721 cells before and after the treatment within the same period. The average elasticity moduli of the SMCC-7721 cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours were 417.71 ± 120.76 Pa, 413.34 ± 145.55 Pa, 838.78 ± 328.44 Pa and 933.4 ± 402.52 Pa, respectively. Compared with the control cells, the average elastic modulus of the SMCC-7721 cells was significantly increased (almost doubled) after four hours of treatment. There was no further significant increase after six hours compared to four hours of treatment, as shown in Fig. 4(d).

In this work, the adhesive force represented the maximum detachment

force between the AFM tip and the cell surface. Fig. 5 shows the average adhesive force and roughness values of the HL-7702 and SMCC-7721 cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours. The average adhesive force values of the HL-7702 cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours were 103.76 ± 2.84 pN, 106.04 ± 2.1 pN, 106.23 ± 2.06 pN and 106.19 ± 1.86 pN, respectively. Accordingly, the average roughness values of the HL-7702 cells were 1096 ± 84 nm, 1213 ± 96 nm, 1191 ± 89 nm and 1109 ± 87 nm. The average adhesive force and roughness of the HL-7702 cells were little changed before and after six hours of treatment with the colchicine solution, as shown in Fig. 5(a). During the same time period and with the solution concentration, the average adhesive force and roughness of the SMCC-7721 cells were gradually increased, especially after four hours, as shown in Fig. 5(a). The average adhesive force values of the SMCC-7721 cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours were 48.44 ± 1.82 pN, 63.65 ± 1.63 pN, 108.78 ± 1.31 pN and 111.62 ± 1.31 pN, respectively. Accordingly, the average roughness values of the SMCC-7721 cells were 1076 ± 94 nm, 1117 ± 64 nm, 1273 ± 109 nm and 1518 ± 104 nm.

4. DISCUSSION

The biomechanical properties of cells have been identified as a key factor related to many diseases such as cancers^{7, 46, 47}. This study aims to better understand the mechanisms occurring during carcinogenesis¹³. In this work, we used an AFM to detect the biomechanical properties of hepatocyte (HL-7702) and hepatoma cells (SMCC-7721) at the nanoscale, before and after the treatment with a colchicine solution for two, four and six hours.

The experiment results clearly showed a significant reduction in cytoskeleton sharpness of HL-7702 cells after six hours of treatment (Figs. 2(a)-(d)). In contrast, during the same period and with the same concentration of colchicine, the cytoskeletal structure of SMCC-7721 cells clearly changed and reassembled (Figs. 2(e)-(h)). The cell mechanics as well as the disease state can be obviously influenced by the changes in the cytoskeletal architecture induced by chemotherapy regimens and anticancer drugs⁹. The microtubule is an essential element in mitosis and it is an ideal target for anticancer drugs. Colchicine is able to destabilize the microtubule^{35, 38, 48}. The results showed that the colchicine changed the cytoskeletal structure of tumor SMCC-7721 cells at the nanoscale, and confirmed that colchicine could inhibit the microtubule polymerization.

The change in the cytoskeletal structure is the intuitive reflect of biomechanical properties. In the present experiment, the average height

(Fig. 2 (i)), the slope of force-indentation curves at the contact critical point between the tip and the HL-7702 cell in the loading stage (Fig. 3(a)), the elastic modulus (Figs. 4 (a) and (c)), and the average adhesive force and roughness (Fig. 5(a)) of the HL-7702 cells remained unchanged before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours. Therefore, the HL-7702 cells remained intact after a six-hour treatment with a normal dose of colchicine. Regarding the SMCC-7721 cells, at the same indentation depth, the indentation force increased with the lengthening of the action time of the colchicine solution (Fig. 3(b)). The SMCC-7721 cells were gradually hardened after the treatment with the colchicine solution within six hours. The average elasticity modulus after six hours of treatment increased by 123% compared with the control cells (Figs. 4 (b) and (d)). The average adhesive force of SMCC-7721 cells (Fig. 5(b)) increased by nearly 125% compared with the control cells after six hours of treatment. Moreover, the average roughness grew to some extent. An increased stiffness of cancer cells is disadvantageous for their motility and metastasis^{8, 14, 16, 49, 50}. In this work, the stiffness of SMCC-7721 cells was increased after the six-hour treatment with the colchicine solution, especially after about four hours. The deformability of the SMCC-7721 cells was thus significantly reduced in the colchicine solution after six hours. The colchicine solution could inhibit the SMCC-7721 cells division and proliferation. In addition,

the cell-surface adhesive force was increased after the six-hour treatment, especially after about four hours. The relationship between the cell-surface adhesion and the deformation of cells is currently not well understood. The adhesive force may serve as a complementary marker for the diagnosis of metastatic cancer⁵. In summary, the colchicine is effective for SMCC-7721 cells over four hours in the normal dose.

The study of the mechanical properties of biological and genetic pathways could help to understand the colchicine-induced effects on human hepatocyte and hepatoma cells at the cellular and molecular levels. This work provides an accurate and rapid method for the detection of the effect of a drug on normal cells and tumor cells. Also, this method appears to be useful for monitoring the change in metastatic cancer cells, thus preventing the emergence and transmission of the disease and the diagnosis of cancer.

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Figure 1. Schematic representation of the imaging and indentation systems. (a) Schematic diagram of the AFM system working in culture. (b) The indentation process using an AFM. (c) The analysis diagram of the loading stage. (d) The analysis diagram of the unloading stage.

Figure 2. The topography and average height of HL-7702 and SMCC-7721 cells. (a) – (d) The topographies of HL-7702 cells in the control condition (a), and when exposed to the colchicine solution for two hours (b), four hours (c) and six hours (d). (e) – (h) The topographies of SMCC-7721 cells in the control condition (e), and when exposed to the colchicine solution for two hours (f), four hours (g) and six hours (h). For both types of cells, the image size was 128×128 pixels. (i) The bar chart represents the average height distributions of HL-7702 and SMCC-7721 cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours.

Figure 3. Diagrams of AFM force-indentation curves. (a) The force-indentation curves of the HL-7702 cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours. (b) The force-indentation curves of the SMCC-7721 cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours. The dashed lines are the slope curves at the contact critical point between the tip and the cells.

Figure 4. Graphs of the elasticity moduli before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours. (a) The distribution of the HL-7702 cells. (b) The average elasticity modulus of HL-7702 cells. (c) The distribution of the SMCC-7721 cells. (d) The average elasticity modulus of SMCC-7721 cells.

Figure 5. Average adhesive force and roughness values of the HL-7702 (a) and SMCC-7721 (b) cells before and after the treatment with the colchicine solution for two, four and six hours.